

Table 1. Response of 5 rice varieties to low temperature (10/6 °C day/night) for 3, 7, 9 d. Hangzhou, China.

Variety	Response		
	3d	7d	9d
IR26	Tip of leaves rolled	All leaves into tubes or withered	Plant dead
Erjiufeng	Tip of leaves rolled	All leaves into tubes or withered	Plant dead
Biyuzaonuo	Normal	All leaves into tubes or withered	Plant dead
Reimei	Tip of leaves rolled	Tip of leaves rolled	All leaves rolled into tubes or withered
Zhonghua 8	Tip of leaves rolled	Normal	All leaves rolled

Table 2. Cold tolerance of 78 rice varieties at the 3-leaf stage. Hangzhou, China.

Tolerant	Ainanzao 39, Zaofengshou, Reimei, Fujikei 131, 81y4-5, Zhonghua 8, Fujikei 137, Akita 32, Wujiegu, Titanio, Yantouqing, Fujisaka 5, Fujikei 130, Longjiangdao.
Medium tolerant	Guiluai 8, Daguangxian, Leyi, Erjiulu 1, Qishirihuodao, Yuanfengzao, Wenzhouqing.
Medium	Zhenlong 13, Simei 2, Ejiunan 1, Chum 84-508, Eza 6, Zhuyunnuo, Yuan 2, Zaoxian 503, Zaolian 31, Fangyangu.
Medium susceptible	Zhenshan 97, Zaoxian 141, Wenge Zhong 83-49, Zhengui 51, Zuo 5 Zhuke 2, IR24, Huazaobai, Butuoai, ZRE8.
Susceptible	Ainanzao 1, Nongsheng, Jinke 5, Qingzhen 16, Hongtu 5, Hongtu 27, Fulianai, Fuyul, Qingganhuang Zhefu 802, Wenxuanqing, Biyuzaonuo, Luhongzao 1, Zhuxi 26, IR26, IR29, IR36, IR60, B3, Hongtu 31, Erjiufeng, Guangluai 4, Erjiuqing, Qingxiaojinzao, H1459, Junlianbao, Fu 8-1, Chaoyang 1, Aichang 25, Zhenyu, Guiluai 3, Erjiulong, Zaojianzaodao, Liantangzao, 5010, Xianfeng 1.

Seedlings of 5 varieties were grown in 50- × 20- × 15-cm plastic trays with 10 cm soil. At the 3- to 4-leaf stage they were subjected to low temperature (10/6 °C day/night) for 3, 7, and 9 d in the incubator. Incubation for 7 d was best for discriminating cold tolerance among varieties (Table 1).

Leaf rolling was the most visible abnormality and might be useful as a sensitive criterion of cold tolerance. It is more simple and practical than using leaf discoloration or dead seedling percentage.

We evaluated 78 varieties at the 3-leaf stage at 10/6 °C day/night for 7 d. The first leaf from the top rolled first, then the second leaf, then all leaves rolled or were fully withered. Varieties could be divided into five cold tolerance groups by leaf rolling symptoms (Table 2):

T = tolerant, all leaves normal
 MT = medium tolerant, tip to 1/2 of 1st leaf rolled (leaflet normal)

M = medium, 1/2 to 2/3 of 1st leaf rolled (leaflet normal)
 MS = medium susceptible, 1st and 2d leaves fully rolled (leaflet normal) or 1st leaf fully rolled
 S = susceptible, all leaves rolled or fully withered.

All of the eight japonicas tested were tolerant. Seven of the 12 tolerant indicas were traditional native varieties. Most of the recommended indica varieties were susceptible. Guiluai 8, Ainanzao 39, and Zaofengshou have been proposed as donors in developing cold-tolerant indica varieties. □

Effect of low temperature on selected rice varieties in Tanzania

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In the Usangu Plains in the south and Moshi and Mombo in the northeast,

low temperature affects the rice crop. Minimum temperatures below 15 °C from late Apr and Aug reduce yield if panicle initiation or heading occurs during the cool period.

We screened 65 Tanzanian varieties from the International Rice Germplasm Center collection for cold tolerance at seedling, panicle initiation, and anthesis (heading) stages in cold water tanks and in the IIRRI phytotron.

Promising cold-tolerant Tanzanian rice varieties.

IRGC acc. no.	Variety	Score ^a at seedling stage	Spikelet sterility (%)	
			Panicle initiation	Anthesis
56208	ES076	3	–	17
56209	ES077 (Shingo)	3	–	–
06485	Afaa Kilombero 1-196	9	10	18
06481	Afaa Mwanza 1-104	9	19	78
56163	ES010 (Supa India)	9	18	16
56164	ES013	9	23	30
56181	ES040 (Turiani)	9	23	15
56184	ES043	9	24	38
56194	ES059 (Bishore)	9	16	13
56195	ES060 (Kialangawa)	9	22	63
56205	ES072	9	15	24
56210	ES078 (Zira)	9	19	–
56213	ES081 (Shindano)	7	17	–
06479	Gamti 1-34	9	37	15
06480	Afaa Mwanza 0-746	9	57	15
06491	Lindi Safari	9	77	6
56161	ES003	9	33	10
56167	ES018 (Gold)	9	26	13
56168	ES018 (Straw)	9	42	8
56183	ES042	7	30	9
56186	ES044 (Wahi)	9	60	13
56192	ES053 (Ringa)	9	–	3
56193	ES054	9	67	10
56214	ES082	9	60	12
07533	HR19	9	52	16

^aStandard evaluation system for rice score.

ES076 and ES077 were tolerant of 12 °C water at the seedling stage (see table). Afaa Kilombero 1-196 was highly tolerant and Afaa Mwanza 1-104, Supa India, ES013, ES040, ES043, ES059, ES060, ES072, ES078, and ES081 tolerant of 17 °C night air temperature for 5 d during panicle initiation.

Gamti, Afaa Mwanza 0-746, Lindi Safari, ES003, ES018, ES042, ES044, ES053, ES054, ES082, and HR19 were tolerant of 21 °C air temperature for 5 d during anthesis.

ES076 showed tolerance at both seedling stage and heading. Afaa

Kilombero 1-196, Supa India, ES040, ES059, and ES072 were tolerant at panicle initiation and heading.

Afaa lines, Supa India, and Kihogo, the varieties commonly grown, are tolerant at panicle initiation, but susceptible at anthesis. □

Response of rice varieties to planting time during the dry season

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In parts of Orissa, rice is grown early in the dry season (DS) using water from streams, tanks, and ponds that dry up in Apr and May. We studied varietal response to different planting times during Dec and Jan. The trials were laid out in a replicated split-plot design in DS 1985 and 1986. Varieties Pathara, Kuber, and Rajani were studied in 1985; Pathara, Rajani, Annapurna, and Shankar in 1986.

Soil was laterite, loamy sand, with pH 5.6, 0.4% organic carbon, 0.04% total N, 12 kg available P, and 150 kg available K/ha. Seedlings were transplanted at 25 d at 15- × 10-cm spacing with 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha. Full P and K and 25% N were applied basal, 50% N at tillering, and 25% N at panicle initiation. Four

Effect of date of transplanting on yield of different rice varieties. Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	1985	1986
<i>Planting date</i>		
5-10 Dec	2.8	2.0
20-25 Dec	3.1	2.6
5-10 Jan	3.7	2.4
20-25 Jan	3.3	2.2
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.1
<i>Variety</i>		
Pathara (OR83-23)	3.1	2.3
Kuber (OR164-5)	3.1	-
Rajani (OR163-104)	3.5	2.4
Annapurna	-	2.6
Shankar	-	1.9
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.1

Temperature profile during the rice-growing season. Bhubaneswar, India, 1985-86.

transplanting dates, at 154 intervals, started 5 Dec 1985 and 10 Dec 1986.

Time of planting affected yield (see table). Transplantings on 25 Dec 1985

and 5 Jan 1987 produced the highest. Late and early planting reduced yield, perhaps because of temperature (see figure). □

Inheritance of seedling stage cold tolerance in 6 indica and japonica crosses

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We used highly cold-tolerant japonica varieties Zhonghua 8 and Reimei as the female parents (P_1) and cold-susceptible indica varieties Ejiufeng, My 821 66, Qinghuaai 6, and Conggui 314 as the male parents (P_2) to make six crosses (two including B_2 , F_1/P_2) between indicas and japonicas in 1985-86.

The seeds were sown in 50- × 20- ×

15-cm plastic trays, one cross (including P_1 , P_2 , F_1 , F_2 , B_2)/tray. Seedlings at the 3-leaf stage were subjected to 10/6 °C day/night, 12 h light (2500-3500 lx)/d for 7 d in the incubator. We used leaf rolling as the criterion for cold tolerance.

All F_1 s showed good tolerance for low temperature. The F_2 and B_2 populations had only R or S seedlings. Segregation of F_2 plants in 6 crosses fit a 15:1 inheritance ratio, B_2 plants in 2 crosses fit 3:1 (see table). That shows that cold tolerance indicated by leaf rolling in indicas and japonicas is governed by two dominant duplicate genes. □